

ATTITUDES OF STUDENTS TOWARDS WRITING: A MIXED METHOD

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 29

Issue 7

Pages: 1057-1078

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2801

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14566745

Manuscript Accepted: 11-05-2024

Attitudes of Students towards Writing: A Mixed Method

Ladymae Ann S. Asis, * Evelyn G. Erellana

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study aimed to describe the lived experiences of first year education students in a local college on the attitudes of students towards writing. This study engaged mixed method design, utilizing parallel convergent approach. The participants of the study were the education students from first year level. There were 258 students who were randomly selected for quantitative and 10 for the qualitative: five (5) for in-depth interview and five (5) for focus group discussion which were purposively selected. In the quantitative phase, the results revealed that the attitudes of students towards writing was high. In qualitative phase, it was revealed that their lived experiences were the effects of emotional and psychological barriers in writing, crucial role of writing within the realm of education, versatility of writing as a tool for expression and interaction, and writing skills development. Additionally, the students' insights shared were building vocabulary and clarity in written communication, passion in writing, effective writing strategies for writing enhancement, and fostering writing excellence. Furthermore, the quantitative data mostly corroborated with the qualitative data.

Keywords: *attitudes of students towards writing, mixed methods, first year education students, Philippines*

Introduction

Writing is considered a primary language skill that all individuals are required to develop (Ramos & Gatcho, 2020). In addition, writing has always been regarded as the most challenging and demanding part of language learning for every student, regardless of their ability, especially when it involves using a second language. The majority of these students do not meet the instructors' expectations in terms of communication and language skills. The students come from diverse backgrounds, use various learning methods, have different language skills and experience levels, as well as unique perspectives, attitudes, and ideas about writing skill. Therefore, it is important to show how these students view writing and their approach towards it (Jabali, 2018).

In Palestine, even after being around English for an extended period, most students studying English as a second language still struggle with writing, as they find it extremely challenging and outside their skill level leading to negative attitude towards writing and English majors and potential majors at An-Najah National University, who make up the study population, are also not exempted. English Department students in this university encounter numerous challenges and hindrances that impact their outlook. For instance, they perceived writing as challenging, especially students struggle with grammar, organization, or expressing their ideas coherently. Also, students feel overwhelmed with academic and extracurricular commitments, leading to a rushed or less invested approach to writing assignments which contribute to the development of negative attitude of students (Jabali, 2018).

In the Philippines, students encounter specific challenges and attitudes towards writing that are influenced by cultural, educational, and socio-economic factors. Many students view writing primarily as a requirement for academic assignments rather than as a means of self-expression or communication which can lead to a lack of enthusiasm and engagement in writing tasks. In addition, students may be apprehensive about making mistakes in their writing due to the emphasis on correctness and accuracy in academic settings. This fear of errors inhibit students' willingness to take risks and experiment with different writing styles and techniques. Also, as emphasized by Yates and Kenkel, writing problem attitudes such as issues with grammar, sentence structure, and interpretation in a different language. Thus, students' proficiency in the language of instruction (often English or Filipino) can influence their confidence and comfort with writing as challenges in language mastery may lead to negative attitudes (Ramos & Gatcho, 2020).

Moreover, college students frequently confronts challenges nowadays, such as those brought by their attitudes towards writing. With these in mind, a study should be conducted that highlights the importance of the attitudes of students towards writing because it does not take much attention in our society. In addition, this study tends to dig deeper on the negative attitudes of students towards writing and the reasons behind it. As a result, I decided to carry out this study to address this issue through a mixed method inquiry on the attitudes of students towards writing. More importantly, since writing is a fundamental communication skill, understanding students' attitudes towards writing, teachers, CHED, college students, and even the governmental bodies would benefit from the findings, gaining a better understanding about the attitudes students towards writing, as well as be able to develop strategies and policies to improve educational outcomes contributing to their active participation in societal discourse, be it in academic, professional, or personal settings.

In connection with this, recent related studies have been conducted to address the problems regarding the attitudes of students towards writing. However, the majority of studies have focused on understanding the dilemma on the present issues of college students who are having the problems in their attitudes towards writing. In relation with this, Dhadhodara et al. (2018) conducted a study entitled "The Writing Attitude of Higher Education Students", which measures writing attitude of higher education students. Another study is conducted by Rushidi (2018) entitled, "Perceptions and Performance: Students' Attitudes towards Academic English Writing", which studies students' written performance affecting their attitudes. Then, another study is conducted by Morgan et al. (2019) entitled,

“University Student Attitudes Towards Peer Review in EFL Writing: A Quantitative Study”, which investigates student attitudes and teacher perceptions regarding peer review in EFL writing at a Japanese university. Meanwhile, these studies have identified the challenges students face in terms of attitudes towards writing, they mostly used either qualitative or quantitative methods. In contrast, this study used a mixed method approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative methods to provide a more valid, reliable, and comprehensive understanding of the students’ attitudes towards writing. Also, the results of this study have significant implications for future research and can serve as a prototype model for future studies, as well as can inform the development of effective dissemination plans for educators and policymakers.

Research Questions

This study investigates the attitudes of students towards writing among first year education students, using a mixed methods research approach. The reason for using this method was to collect numerical and descriptive information at the same time, combine the results, and use them to solve the research issue. This research design utilized the advantages of each data collection method to overcome the drawbacks of the other, leading to a more thorough comprehension of the research issue by analyzing both quantitative and qualitative data together.

1. What is the level of attitudes toward writing of first year education students?
2. What are the experiences of first year education students with regard to their attitudes towards writing?
3. What are the insights of first year education students with regards to their attitudes towards writing?
4. To what extent does the quantitative data corroborate with the qualitative data?

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilized a mixed methods approach, blending qualitative and quantitative elements to offer a thorough analysis of the research issue. George (2021) emphasizes that integrating both methods is vital for the rigor of mixed methods research, and this integration can take place at various stages of the research process. The concept of “mixing” involves combining qualitative and quantitative elements to create a more comprehensive understanding of the research issue.

According to Skamagki (2022), mixed methods research plays a vital role in research beyond mere validation. It enables the integration of multiple research methods, leading to a comprehensive and holistic perspective on the subject of study. This approach not only validates the research but also allows for a more profound understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. By combining the results obtained from different methods, researchers can potentially reveal new insights that might have been overlooked using a single-method approach.

The research design selected for this research utilized a convergent parallel mixed method design. In this design, both kinds of data are gathered simultaneously and treated with equal importance. First, the survey was conducted, then either focus group discussions or one-on-one interviews were carried out. The data sets are examined independently, then combined and interpreted after merging the results. This design is suitable for the study as it intends to investigate the coming together, moving apart, inconsistencies, or connections between the two data sources (Demir, 2018).

The convergent parallel design, also referred to as the convergent/triangulation Design, includes conducting quantitative and qualitative studies simultaneously in the same phase of the research process. In this plan, both approaches are given the same level of importance, allowing them to have an equally crucial impact on solving the research issue. This approach upholds the autonomy of individual studies in data collection and analysis, before consolidating or integrating the findings during the final interpretation (Petrosyan, 2018).

In order to fully comprehend the subject, this research utilized the convergent parallel design, a mixed-method approach. Two elements, qualitative and quantitative, can be used to depict the research process. In a concurrent parallel design, the researcher carries out quantitative and qualitative components at the same time within the research process phase, giving equal importance to both methods, examining each component separately, and interpreting the findings collectively. The researcher’s goal is to combine methods for confirmation and validation by directly juxtaposing quantitative statistical results with qualitative findings. Two collections were studied during the research of data were acquired, analyzed individually, and then compared (Demir & Pismek, 2018).

Under a convergent parallel design, data from qualitative sources such as online interviews (Google meet), screen recordings, and transcriptions, were collected alongside quantitative data obtained from a survey questionnaire. These data were analyzed simultaneously to uncover patterns and insights. In the qualitative stage, experiences of first-year education students towards writing in their learning were analyzed using discourse and thematic analysis. Statistical analysis was used for the quantitative data to obtain findings on the profiling and experiences of first-year education students, as well as the notable variance in the importance and scope of how numerical data supports qualitative data.

Consequently, this research employed a descriptive-comparative approach, which involved comparing and contrasting the collected results to draw meaningful conclusions. By utilizing both quantitative and qualitative research methods, this study aimed to enhance our understanding of attitudes towards writing among first year education students and provide a foundation for effective teaching

strategies and techniques. Hence, the study contains both quantitative and qualitative research methods (Richardson, 2018).

In addition, phenomenological research was employed in this study to enhance the qualitative framework. This approach helped uncover and comprehend the complex environment developing through the participants' experiences. A phenomenology examines the shared lived experience in a specific group. Usually, interviews involve a team of people who possess direct understanding of a particular event, circumstance, or occurrence. Additional types of data like reports and findings can also be utilized (Groenewald (2004) as cited in Ho & Limpaecher, 2022).

On the other hand, the qualitative phase of this study utilized a phenomenological approach, which reflects an epistemological perspective that acknowledges the validity of multiple subjective truths. Qualitative data collection methods such as focus group discussions or one-on-one interviews were also employed effectively to glean insights into the social norms of the community, saturate the data obtained from in-depth interviews, and establish themes based on the researcher's collected data (Hoover, 2021).

Participants

Quantitative Phase

The respondents of this study were first year education students in Kapalong College Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST) during the first semester of S.Y. 2022-2023. They were chosen as the respondents because the study is about attitudes of students towards writing in a Local College. Since the study purports to involve students who are in the first year education program in a local college, it would be fitting and valid to include first year education students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology.

Further, the respondents were determined through sampling, specifically, stratified random sampling to establish randomness and maintain scientific rigor in the study. This method involves dividing population into smaller groups, or "strata," and randomly selecting a sample from each stratum. The per-stratum samples are then combined to create an overall stratified random sample. An alternative to simple random sampling, stratified random sampling ensures that each stratum is represented in the sample and can provide more accurate results when analyzing subgroups within the population (Nguyen et al., 2020).

Table 1.1. Distribution of Respondents

<i>First year Education Students</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
BEED-Generalist	187	67	9.31 %
BSED-English	223	80	11.10 %
BSED-Filipino	191	68	9.51 %
BSED-Mathematics	119	43	5.92 %
Total	720	258	35.83 %

This sampling method was particularly appropriate in this study because the respondents, which are the first year education students are randomly selected based on strata, which in this case are all first year of education program in Kapalong College Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. This also ensures that all of the respondents in the population have equal chances of being selected. The researcher wrote a formal request letter to the College Registrar and gained access to the population of all first year students under education program. The researcher then gathered the data from the population of first year education students to compute the sample. After getting the data, the researcher sent the information to her statistician for computation of the study sample.

The study was conducted among students enrolled in education program from first year level. The institution has a total of 720 first year education students enrolled in first semester, consisting of 187 BEED-Generalist, 223 BSED-English, 191 BSED-Filipino, and 119 BSED-Mathematics. However, the sample appropriate for the study was computed by the statistician, which included 67 out of 187 first year BEED-Generalist students, 80 out of 223 first year BSED-English students, 68 out of 191 first year BSED-Filipino students, and 43 out of 119 first year BSED-Mathematics students.

Table 1.2. Profiles of the Participants

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>1st Year Education Department</i>
IDI-01	Female	BEED-Gen.
IDI-02	Male	BSED-Eng.
IDI-03	Female	BSED-Eng.
IDI-04	Female	BSED-Fil.
IDI-05	Male	BSED-Math
FGD-01	Female	BEED-Gen.
FGD-02	Female	BSED-Eng.
FGD-03	Female	BSED-Eng.
FGD-04	Female	BSED-Fil.
FGD-05	Female	BSED-Math

In total, 258 students were sampled out of the 720 students in the first year education program.

Qualitative Phase

On the other hand, subject recruitment in qualitative research was deliberate. During this stage, purposive sampling technique, which is a type of non-probability sampling, was employed. Individuals who were chosen can provide the most valuable insights for the research inquiries and improve comprehension of the topic being investigated (Moser, 2018). Only 10 participants of first year education students were enjoined in the qualitative phase: five (5) for in-depth interview and another five (5) for focus group discussion. All of them should be a first year education student at KCAST. It should be noted that participants in qualitative phase must not have participated in the data collection of quantitative phase.

Instrument

Quantitative Phase

The researcher utilized an adapted survey questionnaire for attitudes of students towards writing which was adapted from Amri, S. (2022). The said questionnaire used a Five-point Likert Scale which had the following indicators: the following indicators: writing importance for study and career, checking and revising one's writing, writing as a skill and a process, and writing feedback. In a Five-point Likert Scale, participants need only rate and select one option from five (highest) to one (lowest) for each question. Additionally, Likert Scale was effective in evaluating constructs, attitudes, and stimuli that are not easily observable by human senses. Although the questionnaire was modified, it still underwent expert validation.

Qualitative Phase

As to the qualitative phase, a set of researcher-made grand tour questions are devised by the researcher and validated by the panel of experts. This was a set of open-ended questions that are developed based on the results of the survey. This will be used as a compass for the in-depth interviews. Of all the participants who will answer the survey questionnaire in the previous phase, five were purposively selected to undergo the IDI and another five for the FGD. Interviews were suitable in gleaning insights, stories, experiences, opinions and other useful information which could not be expressed with the use of numbers.

Procedure

The data collection process involved multiple steps. The study was carried out according to the following protocols:

Quantitative Phase

During the quantitative stage, a modified survey was utilized to assess students' opinions on writing. It was given to a cohort of education students in their first year. Furthermore, the researcher sent a formal letter to the school principal, seeking permission to carry out the study involving their school and students. The tallied, computed, and analyzed results were compared with the qualitative data findings for confirmation. The study's qualitative and quantitative phases were conducted concurrently.

Qualitative Phase

To collect the first-year education students' feelings about writing in their learning, a one-on-one interview was carried out during the qualitative phase. A guide for interviews was utilized in both the in-depth interview and focus group session. Therefore, in order to guarantee the genuineness of the selection process, the researcher personally contacted and invited the informants, informing them of the tasks to be completed and the time that would be convenient for everyone (Barrett, 2018).

The focus group discussion centered on the exploration of individuals' opinions, experiences, concerns, and desires regarding the specific issues at hand. According to Aspers' (2019), this method typically involves bringing together a group of individuals who share a common characteristic, facilitated by a researcher, to engage in group interactions, exchange perspectives on a specific topic, discuss personal experiences, and provide suggestions. It's important to note that the methodology of focus group research explicitly emphasizes the use of interaction. The discussions took various forms, including one-on-one sessions, and will be recorded through screen recording, with additional notes taken. Google Meet was used as a convenient platform for conducting these discussions.

Furthermore, in-depth or one-on-one interviews were also conducted to provide a valuable opportunity for exploring the perceptions of first year education students regarding their experiences of having attitudes towards writing in learning. Ten (10) students will be purposively selected for these interviews, which will be conducted by the researcher. The in-depth interviews will be screen recorded, lasting from 20 to 30 minutes, and will be carried out using the Google Meet platform.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis

Quantitative data analysis involved using descriptive statistics like the mean to examine respondents' average responses. The collected survey data was used as the foundation for thorough analysis. After collecting the questionnaires, the data was organized and handled appropriately. The survey data was additionally examined with the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) to conduct both descriptive and inferential statistics. These statistical treatments were applied to ascertain the status of mathematics teacher education students.

Qualitative Data Analysis

Regarding the researcher used coding and thematic analysis in analyzing the qualitative data. This required analyzing the patterns and themes that were present in the remarks or comments made by the informants of the participants in both individual and group interviews. The themes were developed to examine the real-life experiences of first year education students about their attitudes towards writing in their learning. The data was carefully analyzed to identify and extract relevant themes that shed light on the research objectives and provide insights into the participants' experiences in this context.

Ethical Considerations

In order to uphold the trust of first year Education students from KCAST, the study prioritized their safety, anonymity, complete protection, and confidentiality as key concerns. Measures were taken to ensure that these ethical considerations are carefully addressed, aiming to maintain the trust of the participants throughout the course of the study.

The researcher diligently adhered to ethical principles including respect for persons, beneficence, justice, obtaining informed consent, and maintaining confidentiality to ensure that ethical standards are met. These principles guided the conduct of the study in a responsible and respectful manner, prioritizing the rights and well-being of the participants (Barrow, 2022).

Respect for persons is an ethical principle that underscores the importance of treating research participants with courtesy and respect, and acknowledging their autonomy in decision-making regarding their participation in a study (Barrow, 2022). This principle necessitates providing participants with comprehensive information about the study and ensuring that they have a clear understanding of the research and any potential risks or benefits. Obtaining informed consent is a crucial aspect of adhering to this principle, as it signifies voluntary agreement based on an informed understanding. By upholding the principle of respect for persons, the researcher can ensure that the study is conducted ethically and in a manner that honors the rights and autonomy of the participants.

Before conducting the interviews, the researcher obtained permission from the participants and arranged the schedule in advance to avoid conflicts with their classes or other obligations. This was done to ensure that the researcher's presence would not disrupt the participants' schedules and to avoid the need for rescheduling or canceling the interviews.

During the conduct of my study, I established a respectful and courteous relationship with the participants and obtained their permission before recording the conversations. I also allowed the participants to ask questions at any time and maintained the confidentiality of the in-depth interviews and focused group discussion. In addition, the participants have the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions. By establishing rapport and acting with courtesy towards the participants, I was able to conduct the study in an ethical and respectful manner.

Consent is a fundamental aspect of research ethics and serves as a way to show respect to research participants. By obtaining informed consent, the participants were made fully aware of the objectives and purpose of the research they were being asked to participate in. Written consent was obtained from the participants, certifying their approval to take part in the in-depth interviews and focused group discussions. They were provided with information about the results and findings of the study, ensuring transparency and keeping them informed (Kidson, 2021).

To ensure the ethical conduct of the study, I provided the participants with letters of permission and consent that outlined the details of the study, including the methods, design, and procedures. These letters were intended to help the participants understand the nature of the study and make informed decisions about whether to participate. Participants who decided not to participate are allowed to leave without any explanations and are assured that their data will remain confidential. The researcher also inform the participants that they have the rights to be informed of the result of the study. By following these ethical guidelines, the researcher was able to ensure that the study was conducted in a responsible and respectful manner.

Beneficence, as an ethical principle, emphasizes the commitment to minimize risks and maximize the well-being of research participants. In this study, efforts was made to ensure the safety and protection of the participants. Anonymity of the interviewees were maintained to prevent any potential risks to their privacy and confidentiality. All files of information was properly secured and not left unattended or unprotected (Wickramasinghe et al., 2022).

To adhere to the principle of beneficence, I took steps to protect the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants' responses and personal identities. To minimize any potential risks, I did not engage in any face-to-face interactions with the participants and instead used a social media platform to communicate with them. By taking these measures, I was able to ensure the well-being and interests of the participants and demonstrate a commitment to ethical research practices.

Furthermore, the data collected from this research study were used only for the purposes outlined in the study. However, the results of the study may also be shared or disseminated through channels such as presentation to the institution, publication in scientific forums or journals, or presentation at conferences, either locally, nationally, or internationally. By disseminating the results of the study, the researcher aims to share the findings and contribute to the broader knowledge base in their field of study.

Confidentiality towards the data, results and findings including the safeguard of participants, different techniques was used. Meaning, all personal identities of the participants are hidden and not shown. All materials including audio records, encoded transcripts, notes,

soft and hard copies of data and others should be eliminated right after the data is analyzed (SAGE Publication, 2018).

To protect the participants' identity and ensure compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, I used discrete coding to denote each participant's responses. This measure involved carefully phrasing any information that could potentially identify the participants in terms of their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location to avoid violating their anonymity. By using proper coding and other measures, I was able to protect the participants' identity and ensure that their privacy was respected.

Justice in the conduct of this study is upheld by ensuring that the rights of the participants who identified themselves as first year education students are respected. Given that the study aimed to investigate the attitudes of students towards writing in the learning of first year education students, no rights of minor students was violated. To ensure fairness and equal opportunity for participation, the researcher utilized random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. First year education students are not coerced into participating and are given the freedom to decline if they so choose. In recognition of their contribution, tokens was provided to the participants, and they are duly credited for their involvement in the research, contributing to the overall success of the study. Additionally, justice was ensured by including only relevant utterances of the participants related to the research objectives and accurately transcribing them (McMullin, 2023).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of data in both quantitative and qualitative phase. The first phase deals with the quantitative part in which it displays the level of first year education students' attitudes towards writing. The second phase deals with the qualitative part in which it was being presented thru a matrix form. The matrix shows the responses of the participants on their lived experiences and insights regarding their attitudes towards writing. Furthermore, the matrix includes the topics examined, fundamental concepts, coding or categories, key themes, and the underlying theoretical frameworks. Also, another matrix displays the blending of the key numerical and descriptive results.

Level of Attitudes Towards Writing of First Year Education Students

The results of the survey conducted are presented here. The overall mean, the items with the highest and the lowest ratings per indicator were given.

Table 2. Level of Attitudes Towards Writing of First Year Education Students

<i>Variables and Indicators</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
A.	Writing Importance for Study and Career		
1.	Master writing in English/Filipino as it is essential for me to succeed in my studies.	4.04	High
2.	Optimize my English/Filipino writing skills since it is a prospective in employment.	3.90	High
3.	Pursue writing regularly to become a competent writer.	3.43	Moderate
4.	Believe that writing session has taught me a lot.	3.92	High
5.	Believe that writing contribute to my ongoing learning and development.	4.07	High
	Category Mean	3.87	High
B.	Checking and Revising One's Writing		
1.	Use appropriate punctuation marks and spelling words accurately.	3.55	High
2.	Proofread my writing to simplify sentences.	3.38	Moderate
3.	Make sure that my work is accurate and coherent.	3.59	High
4.	Consider the readers of my writing.	3.77	High
5.	Revise my writing if my lecturer requests it.	4.16	High
	Category Mean	3.69	High
C.	Writing as a Skill and a Process		
1.	Enjoy writing on topics that I am passionate about and familiar with.	3.91	High
2.	Stay away from writing on unknown, complex, or controversial issues for me.	3.60	High
3.	Continue my writing even if I do not desire it.	3.35	Moderate
4.	Keep my writing as my assignment, even if I am weary.	3.41	Moderate
5.	Believe that writing can convey feelings and a valuable skill.	4.08	High
	Category Mean	3.67	High
D.	Writing Feedback		
1.	Accept negative comments from my lecturer and classmates even if I do not like them.	3.77	High
2.	Feel motivated when my lecturer or classmates provide comments on my writing.	3.81	High
3.	Feel free after gaining positive or negative comments.	3.60	High
4.	Consider negative comments as valuable criticism.	3.51	High
5.	Enhance my writing ability after obtaining substantial comments.	4.06	High
	Category Mean	3.75	High
	Overall Mean	3.75	High

Attitudes Towards Writing

Attitudes Towards Writing. Shown in Table 2 is the level of the attitudes towards writing of first year education students in Kapalong

College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. It obtained an overall mean score of 3.75 with a description of High. This means that the first year education students manifested a positive level of attitudes towards writing. The variable of the study which is the Attitude of Students Towards Writing which has five indicators namely: writing importance for study and career, checking and revising one's writing, writing as a skill and a process, and writing feedback.

Writing Importance for Study and Career. In terms of writing importance for study and career, the category mean is 3.87, which is describe as high. This means that it is highly manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, believing that writing contribute to the ongoing learning and development got the highest mean of 4.07 which is described as high. This means that it is highly manifested by the students. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the participants was pursuing writing regularly to become a competent writer with a mean of 3.43. This rating is described as moderate. This means that it is moderately manifested by the students.

Checking and Revising One's Writing. The checking and revising one's writing was rated by the participants as high, with a category mean of 3.69. This means that it is highly manifested by the students. Revising writing if lecturer requests it garnered the highest rating with the mean 4.16, which is described as high. This means that it is highly manifested by the students. Conversely, proofreading writing to simplify sentences got the lowest mean of 3.38, which is described as moderate. This means that it is moderately manifested by the students.

Writing as a Skill and a Process. The writing as a skill and a process got the category mean of 3.67, which is described as high. This means that it is highly manifested by the students. The item believing that writing can convey feelings and a valuable skill got the highest mean of 4.08, which is described as high. This means that it is highly manifested by the students. Meanwhile, continue writing even if not desire is the lowest rated item which has a category mean of 3.35. This means that it is moderately manifested by the students.

Writing Feedback. In terms of writing feedback, the category mean is 3.75, which is described as high. This means that it is highly manifested by the students. The highest rated item is the enhancing writing ability after obtaining substantial comments which has a category mean of 4.06 and is described as high. This means that it is highly manifested by the students. While, the considering negative comments as valuable criticism got the lowest category mean of 3.51 and is described as high. This means that it is highly manifested by the students.

The Lived Experiences of First Year Education Students with Regards to their Attitudes Towards Writing

Four crucial themes were derived from the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions of participants in response to the first research question. Prior to revealing the findings from the interviews and discussions, specific profiles of participants for the qualitative data collection are purposefully chosen based on certain criteria: they must be first-year education students at KCAST.

Additionally, Table 3 focuses on the first year education students' lived experiences in relation to their attitudes about writing. The main ideas that were found in the participants' responses for research question number one are encompassed in the table.

Table 3.1. *The Lived Experiences of First Year Students with Regards to their Attitudes Towards Writing*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/Categories</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Influence of attitudes towards writing ability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling tired or weary in writing. • Struggling with writing assignments which lowered confidence. • It makes the process arduous or more difficult. • Dislike writing when the topics are longer. • Overwhelmed with the assignments resulted in cramming. • Being bored on topic hinders writing engagement. • Not becoming an effective writer due to dominating negative attitude. • Lose interest in writing when problems are mixed. • Past experiences changed the perspective towards writing. • Afraid to speak due to overthinking people's reaction. • Used words with a sad and critical meaning. 	Writing Hindrances and Emotional Barriers	Emotional and Psychological Barriers in Writing	Self-Determination Theory
Impact of students perspectives towards writing	Engaging into writing is essential for Education students. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is a core access as an education student for teaching. • Basic skill especially in school where students always writing. • Convey ideas clearly and professionally is crucial in the field of education. • Taking notes because it is part of the study materials. 	Emotional and Psychological Challenges in Writing The Vital Role of Writing in Education	Crucial Role of writing within the realm of education	Writing to Learn Theory

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ability to write is very crucial to have for future educator. • As future educators writing is important to communicate effectively and create lesson plans, report, and other educational materials. 	Essence of Writing Skills for Future Educators		
Effects of writing attitudes in relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Writing is a valuable tool for expressing thoughts, sharing information, and learning new things. • Writing as a way of expressing feelings and emotions. • Expressing feelings through writing because of not being vocal. • Writing poems to show love and problems. • Making love letter to express love. • Viewing writing as a venture of effective communication. • Putting ideas together for the readers' to understand what is the author trying to imply. • Useful in communication. • Writing to show empathy, understanding, and companionship. 	Multifaceted Role of Writing	Versatility of writing as a tool for expression and interaction	Sociocultural Theory
Impact of writing attitudes in academic success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studying literatures and communication courses provide a theoretical foundation and strategies for writing. • Writing essays to improve words and grammar. • Teachers and peer support to provide constructive feedback help build skills and interest. • Open to feedback or willing to revise and edit written work. 	Developing Writing Skills Support System to Improve Writing	Writing Skills Development	Cognitive Process Theory of Writing

Emotional and Psychological Barriers in Writing. In the context attitudes towards writing, it was mentioned by the participants that their attitudes towards writing are influenced by a combination of emotional and psychological barriers they encounter. Suggesting that emotional and psychological barriers can disrupt their flow of ideas, inhibit creativity, and lead to procrastination or avoidance of writing tasks. This result in decreased productivity and difficulty in completing writing assignments or projects.

Writing Hindrances and Emotional Barriers. This is the first code of the probed on the first probed issue. Students believed that with their various hindrances exist, it makes writing difficult or challenging. This suggest that students may experience internal challenges that affect their ability to write effectively. They may find writing tedious, challenging, or unenjoyable. This may also reflect low confidence in their writing abilities, may doubt their skills or feel insecure about their capacity to express themselves effectively through writing.

Similarly, BM recognized that they may experience a problem related to their attitude towards writing specifically in taking notes when feeling tired. It implies that when they are tired, they tend to rely heavily on PowerPoint instead of other methods of note-taking. This reliance on PowerPoint may indicate a potential issue with their writing ability, to effectively process and retain information and it may point to a reliance on visual aids rather than engaging in writing. He stated that:

“What attitude sahay kanang sa pagsulat naa gani time nga kapoyon ka in ana mas prefer lang nimo kanang sa powerpoint lang mag base labaw nag sa akoo na part nga kana ganing magtake og kanang notes kanang usahay kapoyan ko mao ng mas moasa nalang gani ko’g powerpoint in ana.” (IDI-02)

(What attitude, sometimes in writing there are times that you will feel tired like that. That you are more prefer to base on PowerPoint especially in my part when taking notes that sometimes I feel tired that I depend more on PowerPoint like that.)

Additionally, JM also recognized that students’ past negative experiences and a lack of support have significantly shaped their attitude towards writing, potentially hindering their ability to develop and excel in this skill. That they struggle with writing assignments which lowered their confidence and when teachers an fellow peers unable to give support in their writing, they may get disengaged and lose confidence in their writing skills as a result. He said that,

“My attitude towards writing have been shaped by negative past experiences. Early on struggling with writing assignments lowered my confidence without having supportive teachers so and fellow peers to provide constructive feedback I can’t build my skills and interest in writing.” (IDI-03)

Moreover, it implies that their attitudes towards writing impacted their writing engagement in different context in a way that students could not write because they feel bored with the topic. This circumstance draws attention that they may struggle with motivation, engagement, and generating original content when faced with writing tasks, particularly those on topics they find uninteresting. As JC stated that,

“Ang kaimpact usahay gani ma konsensya pud ko gamay nga dili gani ko maka sulat gani in ana sa labaw lagig kanang maboringan ko sa topic lagi kay kana laging dika ka sulat lagi nya mag sige ikaw pay mangita ba, in ana gani na part murag sa akooa ba kana ganing gitagaan na gani kag sayon gani nga kanang mga gipakitas screen ba nya imo nalang sulaton nya naa kay feeling nga kanang mabored ka sa topic ing ana gani.” (FGD-03)

(The impact, sometimes I feel guilty because I could not write especially when I get bored to the topic. That you could not write because you are the one to look for it, like that. It seems like for me, it is already presented on the screen and simply given to you for you to copy then you feel bored with the topic like that.)

Emotional and Psychological Challenges in Writing. This is the second code for the first probed issue. The participants imparted that there are internal struggles and mental hurdles that they face during the process that can affect their approach to writing. These emotions may arise from various sources, including pressure to perform, fear of judgment, or personal insecurities. These can create time constraints that limit the amount of time and energy they can devote to writing which may lead to frustration or a feeling of being overwhelmed, affecting their attitude towards writing.

In connection with that, students suggested that their motivation or interest in writing varies depending on their mood and other factors. They describe experiencing fluctuations in their level of interest and engagement with writing, sometimes feeling inspired and wanting to write, while at other times feeling disinterested or lacking motivation. Additionally, the statement hints at moments of uncertainty or hesitation, where the speaker questions their preconceived notions or expectations about writing. As M said that:

“Sometimes depende sa akong mood po. Kay naa gyuy time nga kanang mawad-an bitaw kag gana, pero usahay kay mokalit rapog kuan pud bitaw maghuna-huna ka lami isulat, usahay kay wala, mao to siya. Like kanang ano like magsagol-sagol pud bitaw imong problema bitaw, then naay uban nga unexpected nga kuan ba kanang like usahay kay kanang mag-una imong mga overthinks. Like what if dili ing ani, ana bitaw.” (IDI-05)

(Sometimes, it depends on my mood. Because, there are times that I loss interest, but sometimes I also think about I want to write, sometimes not, like that. Like your problems are mixing, then there are unexpected things like sometimes you prioritize your preconceive thoughts, like what if it is not like that.)

Likewise, students may feel hesitant or shy to express themselves verbally because they fear judgment or criticism from others. As a result, they may find it easier or more comfortable to express their thoughts, feelings, or ideas through writing, such as composing poems or essays. As BM said that:

“Diraa na part kay naa man goy kuan time nga kana ganing maulaw ka isulti, i-express through verbal communication, kay mahadlok kas huna-hunaon sa tao so mao ng sa through writing diraa kanang ma express ba kanang i-express through writing a poem or an essay ana gani.” (IDI-02)

(In that part, there are times that you are shy to speak, expressing through verbal communication because you are afraid about what other people think. That is why we are able to express it through writing a poem or essay, like that.)

Similarly, some students shared their experiences about their attitudes toward writing which can significantly impact the selection of words they used in various contexts. According to them, their perspectives, experiences, and cultural backgrounds shape the words they choose to express themselves. For instance, if they hold a negative viewpoint, they may opt for words that convey sadness or criticism. As M stated:

“Attitudes to writing can influence my choice of words in different contexts because they reflect your perspective, experience, and culture. For example, if I have a positive outlook on something, I may choose to use words that have a happy or optimistic meaning. On the other hand, if I have a negative view, I may choose to use words with a sad or critical meaning.” (IDI-05)

Crucial Role of writing within the realm of education. In the context of role of writing, first year education students imply that the ability to write effectively is fundamental for success not only in academia but also in various professional fields. By emphasizing the essential role of writing, the theme underscores its significance as a skill that individuals who possess strong writing skills are better equipped to excel in their academic pursuits and are more likely to thrive in their future careers, regardless of the specific field or industry.

The Vital Role of Writing in Education. This is the first code for the second probed issue. Participants mentioned the significance and value of writing skills within the educational context. It encompasses the understanding that writing is a fundamental aspect of learning and academic achievement across various subjects and disciplines. Additionally, this category encompass discussions on how writing assignments, essays, research papers, and other written tasks contribute to students' intellectual growth, academic success, and overall learning outcomes.

In relation to that, education students strongly believe in the importance and necessity of writing. They emphasize their viewpoint, asserting that as an education student, they hold writing in high regard, considering it both essential and significant. Indicating their belief that engaging in writing activities is essential for learning and academic success. As CJ stated that:

" Yes po kasi I'm an education student so I believe that it is very essential and it's very important that we engage into writing." (IDI-01)

(Yes, because I am an education student. I believe that, it is very essential and it is very important that we engage into writing.)

Additionally, learners infer that the act of writing is highly important, particularly in the context of education. According to them, writing is not just a supplementary skill but a foundational one for academic success. They underscore the importance of writing as an indispensable tool for learning and functioning within educational environments. As G stated that:

"Writing is important jud siya kay ang writing man gud is a basic skills when about sa school kailangan jud natong magsulat, syempre dapat makabalo ta mosulat." (IDI-04)

(Writing is very important because writing is a basic skill when about school. We really need to write, of course we should know how to write.)

Moreover, students suggested that they frequently write, especially during discussions, as a means of taking notes. This implies that they understand the importance of documenting information for later review and study purposes. As LM said that:

"Yes po, kanang every time nga mag write ko especially kana bitawng discussions, so naga take note ko for para sa akoang studyhan like helpful pud kaayo ni siya para ma enhance akoang writing skills. And lastly po, it help me to my study especially kanang hapit na ang exam I can easily open my notes." (FGD-05)

(Yes, because every time I write especially during discussions, so I take note for me to study. It is also helpful to enhance my writing skills. And lastly, it help me to my study, I can easily open my notes especially when exam is near.)

Essence of Writing Skills for Future Educators. This is the second code for the second probed issue. Participants from Focus Group Discussion mentioned that possessing strong writing skills is essential for individuals aspiring to become educators in the future. That writing skills are not just desirable but crucial for educators to effectively perform their roles. It implies that educators must be proficient in written communication to convey information, instructions, and feedback to students, colleagues, parents, and other stakeholders.

Similarly, students acknowledge that having strong writing skills is essential for educators. They imply that proficiency in writing is not merely advantageous but rather a necessity for individuals in the field of education. As RC said that:

"I think, for me the to have a writing skills is really important it's because as an educator, as a future educator we must have the ability to, we need to have the ability for the writing skills, I guess." (FGD-02)

Moreover, students agree that writing is crucial for educators in their future careers. This indicates an understanding of the role that writing plays in their professional responsibilities. They also highlights the necessity of writing skills for creating essential educational materials such as lesson plans, reports, handouts, and other instructional resources. As SA stated that:

"Yes, writing is important in our future career as educators po. As a educators we need to effectively communicate through writing to create lesson plans, report, and other educational materials po." (FGD-04)

Versatility of writing as a tool for expression and interaction. In the context of versatility of writing, it means that writing is a flexible and multifaceted means of communication that can be used for various purposes and in different contexts. It functions both as a means of personal expression and as a tool for fostering communication and connection with others. It underscores the importance of recognizing and embracing the multifaceted roles of writing in facilitating both self-discovery and interpersonal relationships

Multifaceted Role of Writing. This is the first code for third probed issue. Many of the participants share their experiences about writing as a means for them to convey their thoughts, emotions, ideas, and experiences. It provides them a medium through which they can articulate their innermost thoughts and feelings, explore their identities, and communicate their unique perspectives to others.

In addition, students with a positive attitude towards writing see it as a means to express their thoughts effectively. They view writing as a medium through which they can articulate their ideas, emotions, and perspectives clearly and coherently. They perceive writing as a process that allows them to explore new topics, engage with diverse viewpoints, and deepen their understanding. As JC stated that:

" For me if someone has a positive or a attitudes towards writing they made your writing as a valuable tool for expressing thoughts, sharing information, and learning new things." (FGD-03)

In connection with that, first year education students assert that they are not comfortable or confident in expressing their feelings verbally. Instead, they rely on their writing skills as a means to convey their emotions, thoughts, and feelings. That they experiences struggle with verbal expression of their emotions and thoughts. They may feel inhibited or unable to articulate their feelings effectively through spoken words. As CJ said that:

"Yes po kay as for me I'm not very vocal with my feelings so kanang if naa koy feeling nga if naa koy gusto i-ingon nga dili nako maingon through words I used my writing skills nga diraa nako i-express akoang feelings, akoang emotions and thoughts." (IDI-01)

(Yes, as for me I am not very vocal with my feelings. So, if I have feeling or if I want to say something that I cannot say through words, I used my writing skills where I can express my feelings, my emotions and thoughts.)

In that sense, students use poetry as a means to express emotions and thoughts that they find difficult to convey verbally. They indicate that they turn poetry as a creative outlet for expressing their emotions. They find that writing poems allows them to articulate feelings that they struggle to express verbally, particularly emotions related to love or personal struggles or problems. As JM said that:

"Yes po base on sa akoang ingon nako gaina is nagabuhay kog tula. Diha pud pina-agi sa tula ja nako ginapakita akoang mga emotions nga di nako kaya ipagawas like sa mga about love something ing ana, its about mga problems." (IDI-03)

(Yes, base on what I said earlier I make poems. Through making poems, I show my emotions that I cannot able to express like about love something like that, it is about problems.)

Writing as an outlet of communication/connection. This is the second code for the third probed issue. Participants infer that writing serves as a medium through which individuals can communicate and connect with others. They specified that writing allows them to convey their thoughts, ideas, feelings, and information to others. Also, it facilitates connection between individuals by enabling them to share their experiences, perspectives, and emotions to build rapport.

In that sense, participants suggested that they sees writing as an opportunity for self-expression and artistic exploration. They also emphasizes that they recognizes writing as a powerful tool for communication. They understand that writing allows them to convey their thoughts, ideas, and emotions in a clear and impactful manner. As SA said that:

"My positive attitudes towards writing has shaped my perspectives by viewing it as a creative outlet and a means of effective communication po." (FGD-04)

In addition, students indicate that their positive attitudes towards writing motivate them to embody qualities such as curiosity, perseverance, and commitment. That it awaken their curiosity, exploring ideas, themes, and concepts through writing, which suggests an openness to new perspectives and a desire to learn and grow as a writer. Also, students recognize that writing involves a thoughtful process of organizing and presenting ideas to ensure clarity and coherence for the audience. As RN said that:

"So, my attitudes wakes up my sense of curiosity, perseverance, and commitment to writing. That writing is not just all about putting all of your ideas in words but it is a process of putting your ideas together in a sense that your readers understands what you are trying to imply po." (FGD-01)

Moreover, students shared common experiences in relationships which written communication demonstrates empathy, understanding, and companionship potentially foster deeper connections and enhance the bond between other people. As M said that:

"In relationships, writings that show empathy, understanding, and companionship can drive deeper connection and strengthen the bond." (IDI-05)

Writing Skills Development. This is one of the emerging themes from the responses of the participants from their in-depth interview and focus group discussion with the process focused on enhancing and refining a person's abilities in writing. This suggests that writing skills are not fixed but can be developed and improved over time through dedicated effort and practice. That individuals can strive to become more proficient writers by actively engaging in skill-building activities.

Developing Writing Skills. This is the first code of the fourth probed issue. Students reported the various approaches, techniques, and methods that they employ to effectively communicate their ideas, convey their messages, and achieve their writing goals. Participants encompasses a wide range of techniques and approaches that writers use to plan, draft, revise, and polish their written work, ultimately aiming to effectively communicate their ideas and engage their audience.

In that sense, students' academic studies in literature and communication have equipped them with theoretical knowledge and practical strategies for writing. They suggested that they have learned about concepts such as writing styles, rhetorical strategies, and literary analysis, which form the foundation of their writing skills. As M said that:

"My studies in literature and communication courses provided me with the theoretical foundations and strategies for writing. Regular writing and practices helped me improve my writing skills and learn which styles and strategies work best for me. Reading different types of texts, from academic narratives to creative writing, has given me insight into different writing styles and techniques." (IDI-05)

Furthermore, students have been working to develop their writing skills, particularly in areas such as vocabulary and grammar. They assert that by writing essays, they are able to expand their vocabulary. Through the process of writing and encountering various topics, they have likely encountered new words and phrases, which they have incorporated into their writing. As LM said that:

"...develop nako akoang skills sa pagsulat like for example pagsulat ng mga essay, makatabang siya para ma improve ang akoang mga words, akoang mga grammars po." (FGD-05)

(...develop my skills in writing like for example writing essays, it help improve my words, my grammars.)

Support System to Improve Writing. This is the second code for the fourth probed issue. Participants reported the importance of having a network of resources and assistance in place to enhance one's writing skills. According to them, support system for writing like teachers and peers who offer guidance, feedback, and advice on improving writing skills. These individuals can provide valuable insights, suggestions, and encouragement to help writers develop and refine their craft.

In connection with this, students imply that their writing skills and interest have been positively influenced by the presence of supportive teachers and peers who offer constructive feedback. They acknowledge the role of supportive teachers and fellow peers in their development as a writer. That they highlight the positive impact of receiving constructive feedback from both teachers and peers in shaping their writing abilities and enthusiasm for their writing. As JM said that:

"...having a few supportive teachers so and fellow peers to provide constructive feedback help build my skills and interest." (IDI-03)

Additionally, participants shared their common experiences that they recognize the importance of writing skills in various aspects of life. They likely appreciate the ability of writing to communicate ideas effectively, express oneself creatively, and engage with others intellectually. Because they value writing and enjoy the process, they are more likely to invest time and effort in improving their writing skills. This may involve seeking out resources, practicing regularly, and actively seeking feedback to enhance their writing abilities. As JC stated that:

"I believe that writing is a valuable skill and enjoyable process you are more likely to invest time and effort in improving your writing and then you might be more open to feedback or willing to revise and edit your work and more motivated to practice regularly." (FGD-03)

(I believe that writing is a valuable skill and enjoyable process. You are more likely to invest time and effort in improving your writing and then you might be more open to feedback or willing to revise and edit your work, and more motivated to practice regularly.)

The Insights of First Year Education Students with Regards to their Attitudes Towards Writing

The responses of the participants regarding their attitudes towards writing are shown in Table 3.2. Five crucial themes were identified from the detailed and focused group discussion of participants in response to the second question. The key concepts included codes derived from the topics being examined, which are outlined in the table.

Table 3.2. The Insights of First Year Education Students with Regards to their Attitudes Towards Writing

Issues Probed	Core Ideas	Code/Categories	Essential Theme	Theoretical Support
Realizing students attitudes towards writing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage in writing to cultivate vocabulary. Understand basic concepts of creating sentences, grammar, and vocabulary. Writing thoughts in a clear and organized manner to not detract the message. Set goals to clarify message and strengthening logic ideas. Ability to share ideas and feelings effectively and efficiently. 	Cultivating Vocabulary Through Writing Practice Effective Communication Through Clear Writing	Building Vocabulary and Clarity in Written Communication	Incidental Learning Theory
Students' reflection to meet writing attitudes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Positive mindset, embracing feedback, and continuously striving to improve. Passion in writing creates greater motivation and greater effort. Make the process enjoyable and have meaningful output. Realizing that writing is good. Writing is much emotional experience compare to an intellectual. Like to write if more motivated. 	Writing with Passion	Passion in Writing	Dualistic Model of Passion
Approaches to meet students writing attitudes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide keywords to write information accurately. Guidance to make writing practice engaging and rewarding. Proper instructions on writing process to develop strong foundation in writing attitude. Give real-world examples to understand the relevance of writing for encouragement. Openness into diverse writing. Writing workshop, feedback sessions, and access resources like books and online materials. Explore different genres and form of writing. 	Instructors' Teaching Strategies	Effective Writing Strategies for Writing Enhancement	Self-Regulated Strategy Development (SRSD)
Strategies for writing improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proper feedback to give opportunity to improve writing skills. Need constructive feedback. 	Feedback for Writing Improvement	Fostering Writing Excellence	Expertise Theory

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negative feedback or criticism for writing improvement. • Supportive environment to meet attitudes toward writing. • One on one advising to effectively meet attitudes towards writing. 	Fostering Positive Writing Attitudes Through Support System
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give time to study and practice writing. • Practice writing essays, poems, and other type of academic texts improve writing skills. • Practicing revision and editing to identify and correct errors. 	Dedicated Time for Writing Practice and Improvement

Building Vocabulary and Clarity in Written Communication. The insights of the first year education students in accordance to their attitudes towards writing are being elaborated based from the similar responses given by the participants. Based from the information given by the participants, it is claimed that actively engaging in writing offers two main benefits: enhancement of vocabulary and improvement in clarity of expression. By actively writing, helps expand their vocabulary as they encounter new terms and expressions, and learn to structure their sentences effectively, choose precise words, and organize their ideas logically, resulting in writing that is easier to understand and more impactful.

Cultivating Vocabulary Through Writing Practice. This is the first code for the first probed issue. Participants suggested that actively participating in writing activities leads to improvement in vocabulary skills. They underscores that writing provides opportunities for them to learn new words in context as they use words in their writing, they gain a deeper understanding of their meanings, nuances, and appropriate usage.

Similarly, students indicate that they acknowledge writing that has a positive effect on their vocabulary development. They recognize that through the act of writing, they have the opportunity to encounter and use a wide range of words, which can contribute to expanding their vocabulary. As CJ suggested that:

“I realize nga nindot jud diay kaayo nga mo engage ta into writing kay ma improve our vocabulary.” (IDI-01)

(I realize that it is really nice that we engage into writing because it can improve our vocabulary.)

Moreover, the information gained implies the importance of students grasping fundamental concepts related to writing and language usage. Students emphasizes that understanding basic concepts is essential for them to develop strong communication skills. By mastering sentence structure, idea development, grammar, and vocabulary usage, students can effectively convey their thoughts and ideas in written form, facilitating clear and coherent communication. As M considered that:

“It is important that students understand basic concepts such as building sentences, developing ideas, and using grammar and vocabulary correctly.” (IDI-05)

Effective Communication Through Clear Writing. This is the second code for the first probed issue. Students assume the significance of clarity and brevity in written communication. According to them, clarity and conciseness are essential for ensuring that the intended message is easily understood by the reader. Clear writing eliminates ambiguity and confusion, allowing the reader to grasp the main points quickly and accurately.

With regards to that, participants realize that their attitudes towards writing enable them to express thoughts, ideas, and emotions in a clear and organized manner. They suggested that they value clarity and structure in their writing, recognizing the importance of conveying their message effectively. Also, they understand that excessive verbosity can detract from the message, while overly brief or vague writing can make it dry and uninteresting. As SA suggested that:

“My realization reflecting my attitudes, it allows me to express thoughts, ideas, and emotions in a clear and organize manner. I also come to appreciate the importance of being clear and concise, too much lap can detract from the message while too little can make it dry and uninteresting.” (FGD-04)

Aside from that, they imply that individuals should establish specific goals for their writing endeavors because by setting clear objectives, they can focus their efforts and track their progress towards improvement. They specified that writing skills are not innate talents but can be developed through practice and intentional effort. As what M suggested that:

“Set goals for your writing, such as clarifying the message, expanding vocabulary, or strengthening the logic in presenting ideas. By becoming a good writer, you will have the ability to share your ideas and feelings through words effectively and efficiently.” (IDI-05)

Passion in Writing. In the context of attitudes towards writing, participants have shared their insights regarding of cultivating a passion, positive attitude and appreciation towards the process of writing and written works. They emphasize the significance of maintaining a positive attitude towards writing. This entails approaching writing tasks with enthusiasm, optimism, and a growth mind-set rather than viewing writing as a chore or burden, individuals should see it as an opportunity for creativity, self-expression, and personal growth.

Writing with Passion. This is the first code for the second probed issue. Participants suggested that writing with passion can serve as a

motivational factor, encouraging students to engage actively in writing activities. When they approach writing with enthusiasm and optimism, they are more likely to invest time and effort into their writing endeavors, and can help them persevere through challenges and setbacks.

In connection with that, participants share their insights that they recognize the importance of maintaining a positive attitude towards writing. This could mean staying optimistic even when facing challenges or setbacks. They understand the value of receiving feedback on their writing rather than being defensive or resistant to criticism, they see feedback as an opportunity for growth and improvement. As SA suggested that:

“Reflecting on my attitudes towards writing made me realize the importance of having a positive mindset, embracing feedback, and continuously striving to improve po.” (FGD-04)

To add, students imply that they come to understand the crucial role of attitude in various aspects of life, including writing. Stating that it is necessary in both general activities and specifically in writing. They suggest that having the right attitude can lead to greater motivation and effectiveness in achieving goals. They connect attitude with motivation and effort suggesting that it can generate motivation, leading to increased effort in pursuing goals. This implies that when they are passionate about what they do, they are more likely to invest effort and time into learning and improving in that area. As RC recommended that:

“My realization is that our attitude towards something and even in writing is a must, because as what I said earlier it will lead and create a greater motivation and a great effort for us to do something effectively. So, for example if I am passionate sa akoang ginabuhay sa maningkamot jud ko nga maka tuon and maningkamot jud ko nga maimprove ko ana nga area which kay motivated man ko and then ganahan man ko sa topic so that's it.” (FGD-02)

(My realization is that, our attitude towards something and even in writing is a must, because as what I said earlier it will lead and create a greater motivation and a great effort for us to do something effectively. So, for example if I am passionate to what I do so I will strive for me to learn and I will really strive for me to improve in that certain area which because I am motivated and then I like the topic, so that was it.)

Meanwhile, students infer that they have an epiphany regarding the impact of their attitude on their writing experience. That they identified the significance of approaching writing with positivity and an open mind. As this attitude allows them for greater receptivity to new ideas, feedback, and creative inspiration. By adopting a positive and open-minded attitude, they propose that the overall writing experience can be greatly improved, and that their mindset contributes to their enjoyment of the writing process. As LM supposed that:

“I realized that a positive and open-minded attitude can greatly enhance the writing experience. And it can make the process more enjoyable and the output more meaningful po, that's all po.” (FGD-05)

Emotional Power of Writing. This is the second code for the second probed issue. Students suggested that they have a positive attitude towards writing and values its importance or significance. That they find joy, value, or satisfaction in the act of writing itself. This indicate a positive stance towards the act of writing and its role in personal or professional life.

In relation to that, participants response a sense of personal enjoyment or satisfaction derived from the act of writing. They emphasize the strong positive sentiment towards writing. Additionally, they imply that they believe that others would also come to recognize or experience the same enjoyment if they were to engage in writing, indicating a desire to encourage others to discover the pleasure of writing or to express a belief in the universal appeal of the activity. As CJ supposed that:

“Mas nindot man gud ng kanang magsulat ba nga murag na realize pud nimo ba na mas nindot diay magsulat..” (IDI-01)

(It is really nice to write, like you would realize that it is really nice to write.)

Additionally, students engaged in introspection regarding their attitudes towards writing and has come to a realization. They admitted that writing involves more than just intellectual or cognitive processes. They recognize that emotions such as passion, inspiration, frustration, or catharsis that influence their thoughts, feelings, and expression. As JM suggested said that:

“Reflecting on my attitudes, I've realize that writing is much on emotional experience as an intellectual one.” (IDI-03)

Along with, students specified that emotions, particularly positive ones like motivation and happiness, can significantly impact one's writing experience. They suggest that when they feel motivated and genuinely enjoy writing, their productivity and enthusiasm increase. This implies that positive emotions can serve as catalysts for engagement and effort in writing. As G considered that:

“Yes,dako jud kaayo kay like for example kanang ang imong gi feel or kana imong gibati kay motivated gud kaayo ka, kanang ganahan kaayo ka or dili ka badmood kay good mood ka ganahan kaayo ka magsulat.” (IDI-04)

(Yes, it is really big (impact) because, for example what you feel or your emotion is that you are really motivated, that you really like to or you are not in a bad mood because you are in a good mood, you really like to write.)

Effective Writing Strategies for Writing Enhancement. The insights of first year education students have recognized the use of different teaching methods and a wide range of reading materials to have a positive impact on the development of writing skills. They emphasize

that there isn't a one-size-fits-all approach to teaching writing. Instead, they suggests that employing various instructional methods, such as lectures, workshops, group discussions, peer review, or hands-on activities, can be beneficial in catering to different learning styles and needs.

Instructors' Teaching Strategies. This is the first code of the third probed issue. Within the context of writing, students suggest a focus on the methods and techniques that writing instructors use to teach and develop students' writing skills. Emphasizing the stages of the writing process (prewriting, drafting, revising, editing, and publishing) and providing strategies and guidance at each stage. According to the data gathered, writing is a multifaceted approach that aims to develop students' writing skills through a combination of instructional methods tailored to the specific needs and goals of the learners.

In connection to this, students assert regarding the teaching approach used by instructors. They share that providing keywords instead of writing lengthy sentences or paragraphs can help them take notes more efficiently. This implies a belief that focusing on keywords allows students to capture essential information without spending unnecessary time on transcription. Through recommending the use of keywords, student propose that this approach can help students stay focused and understand the main points of the instructor's discussion more clearly. As BM stated that:

"Akoang ma suggest lang pud sailang panginahanglan no kay mga instructor nga mag hatag nalang og keywords kay instead man gud magsulat kag daghan nga words kana ganing kalas kaayog oras nya makahuman nag storya ang instructor sa discussion mo next slide napud diraa di naka maka human sa imong gisulatan, dili nimo ma finish instead butangan nalag keywords." (IDI-02)

(My suggestion for their needs is for the instructor to provide keywords, because instead of writing a lot of words it is like wasting time. After the discussion of the instructor, the slide will be next again with that you cannot complete what you are writing, you cannot finish instead provide keywords.)

Moreover, participants' response signify the requirement of additional support and instruction in order to effectively engage with and find value in writing practice. In conformity of students' insights, first-year education students may not have sufficient knowledge or experience in employing effective writing strategies independently, therefore they require guidance from instructors or mentors to develop these skills. As JM stated that:

"For first year education students may need more guidance on strategies to make writing practice engaging and rewarding." (IDI-03)

In addition, in order to address the attitudes towards writing among first-year education students, it is necessary to offer them appropriate guidance and instruction on various aspects of the writing process. As, students acknowledge that first-year education students may have varying attitudes towards writing, and it suggests that addressing these attitudes requires tailored support and intervention. This implies that students may benefit from structured assistance in developing their writing skills from initial idea generation to final revisions. As JC said that:

"To effectively meet the attitudes towards writing of first year education, providing with proper guidance and instruction on the writing process including brainstorming, feedback, or editing this helps students develop a strong foundation in writing skills." (FGD-03)

Lastly, students suggested that as first-year education students, there is a need to recognize the practical benefits of understanding how writing skills apply to real-world situations. Additionally, they emphasize the importance of motivation and encouragement to explore various genres and forms of writing. That first-year education students may benefit from understanding how writing skills are applicable beyond the classroom which includes recognizing how writing is used in professional settings, everyday communication, and various aspects of life. As what RC said that:

"I think as first year education student we need to know the benefits from understanding the relevance in the real world applications of writing. Also in motivation and encouragement to explore different genres and forms of writing po." (FGD-02)

Exposure to different written texts. This is the second code for the third probed issue. As participants highlighted that exposure to different texts allows them to encounter diverse perspectives, ideas, and viewpoints. This can help improve language proficiency and comprehension skills, and beneficial for academic and professional development.

In connection, students believe that they need a significant amount of exposure to various types of writing in order to effectively address their attitudes towards writing and to improve as a writer. They suggest that encountering a wide range of writing styles, genres, and forms is crucial for their development as a writer. This exposure could include reading different types of literature, studying various writing techniques, and exploring diverse writing contexts. As what Participant 4 observed that:

"...much exposure pa to diverse writing experience to effectively meet my attitudes towards writing. Para mas ma improve pa gud ko as a writer." (IDI-04)

(...much exposure to diverse writing experience to effectively meet my attitudes towards writing. For me to really improve as a writer.)

On top of that, participants point out that first-year education students may require extra assistance in addressing their attitudes towards writing. That there is a recognition that first-year education students may face challenges or barriers in their attitudes towards writing that require additional assistance. This could include issues such as lack of confidence, limited exposure to diverse writing experiences,

or difficulty with certain aspects of the writing process. The responses outlines potential support measures that could be beneficial for addressing these attitudes towards writing. This includes writing workshops, where students can receive instruction and guidance on various aspects of writing, feedback sessions to provide constructive criticism and encouragement, and access to resources such as books and online materials to supplement their learning. As LM supposed that:

“First year education students might need additional support to effectively meet their attitudes towards writing, this could include writing workshops, feedback sessions, and access to resources like books and online materials po, that’s it.” (FGD-05)

Fostering Writing Excellence. This is one of the emerging themes from the responses of the participants from their in-depth interview and focus group discussion which signify that writing skills are not solely developed through individual effort but also through collaboration. This could involve interactions with peers, instructors, mentors, or writing groups, where individuals engage in discussions, share ideas, and provide feedback to each other. It emphasizes the importance of a multifaceted approach to writing development that leverages both collaborative and individual efforts.

Feedback for Writing Improvement. This is the first code of the fourth probed issue. In-depth interview and focus-group discussion participants imparted the importance of providing feedback as a means to enhance writing skills. They emphasize that feedback is essential for them to identify their strengths and weaknesses in their writing. It helps them understand what aspects of their writing need improvement, whether it be clarity, organization, grammar, or style. Consequently, students require feedback from both teachers and peers to understand how to improve their writing. Feedback provides specific guidance on areas of strength and areas needing improvement, helping students develop a clearer understanding of their writing abilities and how to enhance them. Reporting, or showcasing one's writing, is emphasized as an important aspect of the writing process as it provides students with the opportunity to demonstrate their writing skills and receive feedback in a structured manner. As M said that:

“Students need proper feedback from their teachers or fellow students to know to improve their writing reporting is also important so that they have the opportunity to show their writing skills.” (IDI-05)

Moreover, participants suggest that as a first-year education student, they need a supportive environment and constructive feedback to thrive academically and personally. They underscore the importance of having a supportive environment conducive to their growth and learning. This environment may include supportive peers, understanding instructors, and resources that cater to their needs which denote that feeling supported and encouraged contributes to their overall well-being and success as a student. As G said that:

“So for me as a first year education students kailangan jud nako og kanang kumbaga supportive environments, constructive feedback....” (IDI-04)

(So, for me as a first year education students, I really need to like somehow a supportive environment, constructive feedback...)

Additionally, participants present their acknowledgement towards the importance of being open to criticism and feedback in order to improve both their writing skills and themselves as writers. They point out the necessity of accepting negative feedback or criticism from others which convey willingness to listen to others' perspectives, even if they are critical, and to consider them as opportunities for growth rather than personal attacks. As CJ said that:

“Yes po kay there’s always room for change so kanang need pud nato nga modawat ta og mga negative or mga criticism from others kay para ma-improve pud atoang writing ug atoang sarili into writing po.” (IDI-01)

(Yes, because there is always room for change. So, we really need to accept negative or criticism from others to improve our writing and our self into writing.)

Fostering Positive Writing Attitudes Through Support System. This is the second code for the fourth probed issue. Participants emphasized the network of individuals, resources, and structures that provide encouragement, guidance, and assistance to writers in their writing endeavors. They highlight that support system in writing provides them encouragement and motivation to pursue their writing goals. This may come from peers, mentors, instructors, friends, or family members who offer positive reinforcement and belief in their writing abilities.

Similar to that, students imply the importance of ensuring that first-year education students are actively engaged in writing during classes. This suggests a desire to promote active participation and involvement in writing activities as part of the learning process. They also specified the role of instructors or teachers in creating a supportive writing environment, including fostering a positive and inclusive classroom atmosphere where students feel comfortable expressing their ideas and opinions. As JC said that:

“To ensure writing engagement of first year education students during classes, instructors or teachers create a supportive writing environment because foster positive and inclusive classroom environment where student feel comfortable expressing their ideas, and taking grace in their writing.” (FGD-03)

To add, participants infer that first-year education students need support systems, such as writing workshops or one-on-one advising, to effectively address their attitudes towards writing. According to them, writing workshops and one-on-one advising as examples of support systems can be beneficial for first-year education students as it provide opportunities for structured instruction, practice, and

feedback, while one-on-one advising offers personalized guidance and support tailored to individual student needs. As SA said that:

“For me po, first year education student po needs support systems such as writing workshops or one on one advising po, to effectively meet the attitude po towards writing.” (FGD-04)

Dedicated Time for Writing Practice and Improvement. This is the third code for the fourth probed issue. Participants entailed the act of independently engaging in writing activities to improve one's writing skills and foster a positive attitude towards writing. They suggests that instead of relying solely on formal instruction or external feedback, individuals actively engage in writing activities on their own initiative. Through self-practice, writers have the opportunity to hone their writing skills through regular practice.

Similarly, participants underscore that as education students, allocating time for studying and practicing writing is crucial due to its importance in future professional roles, particularly if they become teachers. They embrace the significance of writing skills in the field of education. By emphasizing the need to give time for studying and practicing writing, the statement suggests a commitment to self-improvement. As JM said that:

“I think ang need gyud nato nga mga education student is kanang mahatag ta og time saatong sarili nga mag study and magpractice og writing kay very essential nga in future labaw na kung mahimo natang mga maestra ngin ana po.” (IDI-01)

(I think, what we really need as education student is that, giving time for ourselves to study and practice in writing because it is very essential in the future especially if we become teachers.)

To add, students entail that consistent practice is crucial for enhancing writing skills. They give emphasis to the significance of regular writing practice in improving writing abilities, suggesting that proficiency in writing is not achieved overnight but requires ongoing effort and dedication. By mentioning various types of writing such as essays, poems, news, and academic texts, the statement suggests that practicing different forms of writing can contribute to overall skill development. This implies that exposure to a variety of writing genres helps writers develop versatility and adaptability in their writing. As M said that:

“Regular writing practice is essential to improve writing skills. This may include writing essays, poems, news, and other types of academic texts.” (IDI-05)

Lastly, base on the responses of first year education students, practicing revision and editing is crucial for them to develop the skills needed to identify and correct errors in their writing. By engaging in revision and editing exercises, students learn to recognize errors and weaknesses in their writing which propose that through practice, students can develop a critical eye for identifying areas that need improvement. As M said that:

“Practicing revision and editing is important so that students learn to identify and correct errors in writing. This will give ability to improve the quality of writing.” (IDI-05)

(Practicing revision and editing is important so that students learn to identify and correct errors in writing. This will give ability to improve the quality of writing.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The current research investigates the viewpoints of first-year education students at a local college towards writing using a mixed methods approach with convergent parallel design. The third research inquiry in the study is focused on confirming the results obtained from both the quantitative and qualitative phases.

Table 4 displays the main quantitative and qualitative results alongside the key aspects of the study in the first column, with the corresponding quantitative and qualitative findings listed in the second and third columns. The quantitative findings typically have the highest mean values, while the qualitative results confirm or refute the responses identified in the quantitative phase. The fourth column indicates the type of data integration, while the fifth column illustrates the ethical implications drawn from the data discussed in earlier columns.

Table 4. Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

Aspect Or Focal Point	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Nature Of Data Integration	Axiological Implications
Writing Influenced Academic Success	From Table 2 on writing importance for study and career item 1 which is about student mastering writing in English/Filipino as it is essential for their success in their studies (M=4.04) which is rated as high.	Table 3 on the vital role of writing in education under the theme of crucial role of writing within the realm of education	Merging – converging	The high rating for writing importance for study and career highlights the importance of writing skills in both academic pursuits, honing students' writing abilities to excel academically.
Essence of Effective Writing Skills	From Table 2 on writing importance for study and career item 2 about students optimizing English/Filipino writing skills as it is a prospective in	Table 3 on essence of writing skills for future educators under the crucial role	Merging – converging	It underscores that writing skills are essential for future educators. Students who pursue as future educators, the ability to write well is

	employment (M=3.90) which is rated as high.	of writing within the realm of education		likely to be highly relevant and valuable in the employment landscape.
Needs of Students for Effective Writing	From Table 2 on checking and revising one's writing item 2 about students who proofread their writing to simplify their sentences (M=3.38) which is rated as moderate.	Table 3.1 on cultivating vocabulary through writing practice in building vocabulary and clarity in written communication	Merging – converging	Actively engaging in writing activities contributes to the enhancement of vocabulary skills among students. This practice implies that proofreading for sentence simplification can have a positive impact on vocabulary development and this practice is rated as moderate in terms of its effectiveness.
Developing One's Writing Ability	From Table 2 on checking and revising one's writing item 3 about the students who make sure that their work is accurate and coherent (M=3.59) which is rated as high.	Table 3 on developing writing skills under the theme of writing skills development	Merging – converging	A better grasp of the importance of developing writing skills that involve thorough checking and revising to ensure accuracy and coherence in students' work. It proposed that these practices are rated highly in terms of their effectiveness, emphasizing their role in fostering strong writing skills.
Importance of Writing in Relationships	Table 2 on checking and revising one's writing item 4 about students who consider their readers of their writing (M=3.77) which is rated as high.	Table 3 on writing as an outlet of communication /connection under the theme of versatility of writing as a tool for expression and interaction	Merging – converging	The high rating of its effectiveness emphasizes that writing is not just a solitary activity but a way for individuals to express themselves and engage with others, ensuring clarity and relevance for their audience.
Dealing Difficulties in Writing	From Table 2 on writing as a skill and a process item 4 about students who keep writing as their assignment, even if they are weary (M=3.41) which is rated as moderate.	Table 3 on writing hindrances and emotional barriers under the theme of emotional and psychological barriers in writing	Merging – converging	It brings attention to writing hindrances and emotional barriers as both a skill and a process. That despite feeling tired or weary, students continue to work on their writing assignments, suggesting a level of dedication or commitment to completing the task, even in the face of challenges or emotional and psychological barriers.
Students Perspectives Towards Writing	Table 1.2 on writing as a skill and a process item 5 about students who believe that writing can convey feelings and a valuable skill (M=4.08) which is rated as high.	Table 3 on multifaceted role of writing under the theme of versatility of writing as a tool for expression and interaction	Merging – converging	Their relationship underscores writing as a multifaceted, emphasizing its significance as both a skill and a process. It highlights that some students see writing not just as a mechanical task but as a creative outlet through which they can communicate their innermost thoughts and sentiments.
Ensures Students Writing Engagement	From Table 2 on writing feedback item 1 about students who accept negative comments from lecturer and classmates even if they do not like them (M=3.77), item 3 about students who feel free after gaining positive or negative comments (M=3.60), item 4 about students who consider negative comments as valuable criticism (M=3.51), and item 5 about students who enhance their writing ability after obtaining substantial comments (M=4.06) which are all rated as high.	Table 3 on feedback for writing improvement under the theme of fostering writing excellence	Merging – converging	The importance of feedback for improving writing skills within the context of collaborative writing development suggests that writing improvement is not solely dependent on individual practice but also involves elements such as feedback, support structures, and collaborative efforts

Writing Influenced Academic Success. In the quantitative phase, the specific item on writing importance for study and career rated as high is master writing in English/Filipino as it is essential for me to succeed in my studies. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is themed as crucial role of writing within the realm of education. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Essence of Effective Writing Skills. In the quantitative phase, the specific item on writing importance for study and career, optimize my English/Filipino writing skills since it is a prospective in employment, is rated as high. This result is connected to the qualitative findings under the crucial role of writing within the realm of education. Hence, the qualitative data converges quantitative in this aspect.

Needs of Students for Effective Writing. In the quantitative phase, on checking and revising one's writing about proofread my writing to simplify my sentences, is rated as moderate by the respondents. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is the building vocabulary and clarity in written communication. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Developing One's Writing Ability. The specific item on checking and revising one's writing, which rated as high is make sure that my work is accurate and coherent. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is under the theme writing skills development. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Importance of Writing in Relationships. The specific item on checking and revising one's writing rated as high is consider the readers of my writing. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is under the theme versatility of writing as a tool for expression and interaction. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Dealing Difficulties in Writing. The specific item on writing as a skill and a process rated as moderate is keep my writing as my assignment, even if I am weary. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is under the theme emotional and psychological barriers in writing. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Students Perspectives Towards Writing. The specific item on writing as a skill and a process rated as high is believe that writing can convey feelings and a valuable skill. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is under the theme versatility of writing as a tool for expression and interaction. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Ensures Students Writing Engagement. In the quantitative phase, on writing feedback about accept negative comments from my lecturer and classmates even if I do not like them, feel free after gaining positive or negative comments, consider negative comments as valuable criticism, and enhance my writing ability after obtaining substantial comments, all are rated as high by the respondents. These results are connected with the qualitative findings, which is the fostering writing excellence. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Conclusions

The study's results led to the following conclusions being made:

First, the level of students' attitudes towards writing is high in terms of writing importance for study and career, checking and revising one's writing, writing as a skill and a process, and writing feedback. Hence, this indicate that the indicators of attitudes towards writing are always manifested by the first year education students.

Second, the qualitative data was thematically analyzed using the responses gathered from conducting in-depth interviews (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD). The findings provided additional insights into the perspective of the students regarding their experiences with regards to their attitudes towards writing. Qualitatively, first year education students have been experiencing different situations which contribute to their attitudes towards writing. The following themes were emerged: Emotional and Psychological Barriers in Writing, Crucial Role of Writing within the Realm of Education, Versatility of Writing as a Tool for Expression and Interaction, and Writing Skills Development.

Third, from the participants responses, other themes are identified which show the insights shared of first year education students with regards to their attitudes towards writing. The following are the themes: Building Vocabulary and Clarity in Written Communication, Passion in Writing, Effective Writing Strategies for Writing Enhancement, and Fostering Writing Excellence.

Lastly, to better understand the impact of students' experiences with regards to their attitudes towards writing, thematic analysis was conducted on the responses to validate the study's quantitative findings. The results from both phases are combined according to the nature blueprint. The quantitative findings revealed that students' attitudes towards writing align with the qualitative data collected. Both the quantitative and qualitative findings both confirm that their attitudes towards writing it have negative side effects, the positive effects, and benefits of their attitudes towards writing where much more significant.

The study's results led to the creation of the following recommendations:

Since the level of the students attitudes towards writing reveal that among the four indicators of students attitudes towards writing, the writing feedback have the lowest mean which affects the attitudes of students towards writing, it is recommend that students may approach writing feedback with an open mind, recognizing that it is intended to help them improve their writing skills. They should

remember that receiving constructive criticism is a normal part of the writing process and an opportunity for growth. They may also develop self-editing skills by reviewing their own writing critically before seeking feedback. Remember to proofread their drafts carefully for errors in grammar, punctuation, spelling, and syntax, and to make revisions for clarity, coherence, and organization independently.

Moreover, based from the qualitative phase results on the lived experiences of first year education students with regards to their attitudes towards writing, students may acknowledge and normalize the emotions they may experience while writing such as self-doubt or perfectionism because many writers including experienced professionals encounter similar emotions and that is a natural part of the writing process. They may also set realistic expectations for their writing process and outcomes, and focus on making gradual progress and improvement overtime rather than expecting perfection or instant results. In addition, they may practice free writing as a way to generate ideas and improve fluency as it is a valuable tool for brainstorming, exploring ideas, and getting started with writing. Hence, from the good experiences they have, students may learn to continue to integrate positive attitudes towards writing, setting a strong foundation for academic success and professional growth in their future careers.

Furthermore, those differentiated insights shared of first year education students with regards to their attitudes towards writing may be used to meet their attitudes towards writing and future endeavors. Also, new strategies may form for students to utilize such as exposure to various genres and writing styles to help them encounter new vocabulary and improve their understanding of how to express ideas clearly. In addition, the researcher recommends the intensification integration of effective writing strategies by educators through teaching students about the writing process, including pre-writing, drafting, revising, editing, and publishing to encourage them allocate time for each step in their writing. There may be conduct of writing workshops where students can receive focused instruction and feedback on specific aspects of writing, providing opportunities for guided practice and individualized support to help students improve their writing skills. By implementing these, it can help first year education students foster excellence in their writing, empowering them to become confident and effective communicators in their academic and professional pursuits.

Lastly, it is also being recommended for the students to demonstrate their own passion and enthusiasm for writing by sharing their own writing experiences, success, and challenges, serves as a positive role model for other students and show them that writing can be an enjoyable and rewarding endeavor. Also, the researcher recommend for educators to integrate writing assignments and activities into various subject area to demonstrate the importance of writing skills across disciplines, showing students how writing can be used as a tool for learning, reflection, and expression in all areas of study. These may help the students develop positive attitudes towards writing and foster a lifelong appreciation for the power and value of written communication.

References

- Abbas, A.M. & Tawfeeq, H.M. (2018). The Effects of Direct and Indirect Corrective Feedback on Accuracy in Second Language Writing. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343381429_The_Effects_of_Direct
- Aka, N. (2020). Incidental learning of a grammatical feature from reading by Japanese learners of English as a foreign language. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0346251X19306566>
- Amour, L.K. (2023). How can you use writing to connect with your audience and build relationships? <https://www.linkedin.com/advice/3/how-can-you-use-writing-connect-your-audience#:~:text=It%20helps%20your%20audience%20become,credibility%20and%20reliability%20over%20time>.
- Amri, S. (2022). Exploring EFL Higher Education Learners' Attitudes Toward Writing Skills Process. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C
- Aspers, P. (2019). What is Qualitative in Qualitative Research - PMC. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6494783/>
- Barrett, D. (2018). Data collection in qualitative research. <https://ebn.bmj.com/content/21/3/63>
- Barrow, JM. (2022). The Research Ethics - StatPearls. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK459281/>
- Carless, D. (2019). Longitudinal perspectives on students' experiences of feedback: a need for teacher–student partnerships. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/07294360.2019.1684455>
- Cherry, K. (2022). What Is Self-Determination Theory. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-self-determination-theory-2795387>
- Cherry, K. (2022). What Is Self-Determination Theory? How Self-Determination Influences Motivation. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-self-determination-theory-2795387>
- Clark, V. & Ivankova, N. (2017). A conceptual framework for the field of mixed methods research. *Mixed Methods research: A guide to the field* (pp. 1-2). SAGE Publications, Inc. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781483398341>.
- Creswell, J. W. (2008). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. Upper Saddle River, N. J.: Pearson/Merill Education

- Dabrowski, J., & Marshall, T.R. (2018). Motivation and Engagement in Student Assignments: The Role of Choice and Relevancy. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED593328.pdf>
- Davidson, M.J. (2021). Towards an Understanding of Program Writing as a Cognitive Process: Analysis of Keystroke Logs. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3446871.3469774>
- Delve. Ho, L., & Limpaecher, A. (2022). What is Phenomenological Research Design? Essential Guide to Coding Qualitative Data. <https://delvetool.com/blog/phenomenology>
- Demir, S.B., & Pismek, N. (2018). A convergent parallel mixed-methods study of controversial issues in social studies classes: A class of ideologies. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practices*, 18(1), 119-149. <https://doi.org/10.12738/estp.2018.1.0298>
- Demir, SB. (2018). A Convergent Parallel Mixed-Methods Study of Controversial. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1179818.pdf>
- Dhadhodara, N. & Joshi, B. (2018). The Writing Attitudes of Higher Education Students. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325386595_
- Ekanayaka, W.E., & Ellis, R. (2020). Does asking learners to revise add to the effect of written corrective feedback on L2 acquisition? <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0346251X203>
- George, T. (2023). What is a Focus Group | Step-by-Step Guide & Examples. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/focus-group/>
- Graham, S., & Harris, K.R. (2023). The role and development of self-regulation in the writing process. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&as_ylo=2020&q=Developing+One%27s+Writing+Ability&btnG=#d=gs
- Jabali, O. (2018). Students' attitudes towards EFL university writing. [https://www.cell.com/heliyon/pdf/S2405-8440\(18\)33085-8.pdf](https://www.cell.com/heliyon/pdf/S2405-8440(18)33085-8.pdf)
- Karim, K., & Nassaji, H. (2020). The revision and transfer effects of direct and indirect comprehensive corrective feedback on ESL students' writing. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&as_ylo=2020&q=checking
- Kendra Cherry, K. (2022). What Is Sociocultural Theory? <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-sociocultural-theory-2795088>
- Kidson, M. (2021). The importance of transparency in research reporting. <https://www.uoguelph.ca/hnru/news/2021/10/importance-transparency-research-reporting>
- Köhler, D.P., & Rausch, A. (2022). Expertise Development in the Workplace Through Deliberate Practice and Progressive Problem Solving. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12186-022-09301-y>
- Kuiken, F., Dijk, A.V., & Gelderen, A.V. (2022). Which types of instruction in writing-to-learn lead to insight and topic knowledge in different disciplines? A review of empirical studies. [https://bera-journals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/rev3.3359#:~:text=Three%20theories%20about%20the%20process,learn%20by%20Klein%20\(1999\).](https://bera-journals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/rev3.3359#:~:text=Three%20theories%20about%20the%20process,learn%20by%20Klein%20(1999).)
- Lincoln, Y. S. & Guba E. G. (1985) *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Beverly Hills, Calif: SAGE Publications. <https://books.google.com.ph/>
- Lissie Hoover, L. (2021). 5 Qualitative Research Designs and Research Methods Dissertation Resources. <https://www.gcu.edu/blog/doctoral-journey/5-qualita>
- Marantika, M.Y., & Tustiawati, A.M. (2023). Students' Perspectives on Their Writing Skills and The Application of Process Writing Approach in the Academic Writing Classroom. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369371673_Students'_Perspectives_on_Their_Writing_Skills_and_The_Application_of_Process_Writing_Approach_in_the_Academic_Writing_Classroom
- McMullin, C. (2023). Transcription and Qualitative Methods: Implications for Third. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11266-021-00400-3>
- Morgan, B., Fuisting, B., & White, J. University Student Attitudes Towards Peer Review in EFL Writing - LEiA. https://leia.org/LEiA/LEiA%20VOLUMES/Download/LEiA_
- Nusrat, A., Ashraf, F., & Narcy-Combes, M.F. (2019). Effect of Direct and Indirect Teacher Feedback on Accuracy of English Writing: A Quasi-Experimental Study among Pakistani Undergraduate Students. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338195755_Effect_of_Direct_and_Indirect
- O'Keefe, P.A., Dweck, C.S., & Walton, G.M. (2018). Implicit Theories of Interest: Finding Your Passion or Developing It? <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6180666/>
- Pariwat Imsa-ard, P. (2020). International Journal of Linguistics and Translation Studies. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&as_ylo=2020&q=Essence+of+Effective+Writing+Skills&btnG=#d=gs_

- Petrosyan, Y. (2018). Assessing research protocols: Mixed methods research. In *Methods Workshop for the Ministry of Health and Long-Term Care*.
- Ramos, E.T. & Gatcho, A.R. (2020). Common Writing Problems and Writing Attitudes among Freshman University Students in Online Learning Environments: An Exploratory Study. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/328948->
- Richards, R.G. (2018). Helping Students Who Struggle to Write: Classroom Compensations. <https://www.ldonline.org/ld-topics/writing-spelling/helping-students-who-struggle-write-classroom-compensations>
- Roslyn Petelin Routledge, R.P. (2021). *How Writing Works: A field guide to effective writing*. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&as_ylo=2020&q=proofreading+and+editing+of+Students+for+Effective
- Rushidi, J. (2018). Students' Attitudes towards Academic English Writing. <https://sciendo.com/pdf/10.2478/v10306-012-0013-6>
- Sarwat, S., Ullah, N., Shehzad, H.M., Tariq, A., & Bhuttah, M. (2021). Problems and Factors affecting students English writing skills. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&as_ylo=2020&q=Essence+of+Effective+Writing+Skills&btnG=#d=gs_
- Silva, C., Almeida, T., & Farroupas, S. (2018). The Impact of Revision and Feedback on the Quality of Children's Written Compositions. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/315494023_
- Skamagki, G. (2022). The concept of integration in mixed methods research: a step-by-. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09593985.2022.2120375>
- Sweller, J. (2011). Cognitive Load Theory. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/psychology/cognitive-load-theory>
- Taub, M., Banzon, A.M., Outerbridge, S., Walker, L.R., Olivera, L., Salas, M., & Schneier, J. (2023). Towards scaffolding self-regulated writing: implications for developing writing interventions in first-year writing. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11409-023-09357-8>
- The Society for Education and Training (2023). The importance of cognitive load theory (CLT). <https://set.et-foundation.co.uk/resources/the-importance-of-cognitive->
- Ting, S., Chuang, W., & Yi, W. (2022). The Effectiveness of Self-Regulated Strategy Development on Improving English Writing: Evidence from the Last Decade. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1353571>
- Trent University. (2023). The Importance of Revising Your Paper. <https://www.trentu.ca/history/importance-revising-your-paper>
- United States Air Force Website (USAFW). (2018). Writing Your Way to Academic Excellence: the Art of Effective Writing. <https://www.learningprofessionals.af.mil/Resources/Student-Success-Center/Writing/>
- Vaidis, D. & Bran, A. (2020). Cognitive Dissonance Theory. <https://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/display/document/>
- Van der Klei, F.M. (2020). Evaluation of the 'Feedback Engagement Enhancement Tool' to examine and enhance students' engagement with feedback on their writing. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0191491X20301553>
- Wahyuni, S. (2018). The Effect of Different Feedback on Writing Quality of College Students with Different Cognitive Styles
- Wexler, N. (2019). Writing and Cognitive Load Theory. <https://researched.org.uk/2019/06/24/writing-and-cognitive-load-theory/>
- Wickramasinghe, V. & Wickramarachchi, G. (2022). *Ethics in Qualitative Research* SAGE Publication. (2018). *FUNDAMENTALS OF QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS*
- Wright, K.L., Hodges, T., & McTigue, E. (2019). A validation program for the Self-Beliefs, Writing-Beliefs, and Attitude Survey: A measure of adolescents' motivation toward writing. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?as_ylo=2019&
- Writes, C.S. (2018). Why writing letters is still important. <https://writingcooperative.com/why-writing-letters-is-still-important-2346d25d6679>
- Yenti, D., Abdi, R., & Payakumbuh, P. (2022). College Students' Attributions of Their Academic Success and Failure In Writing Skill. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&as_ylo=2020&q=Academic+Success+influence+writing+&btnG=#d=gs

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Ladymae Ann S. Asis

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Evelyn G. Erellana, MAEd

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines